

The Influence of Green Management and Correspondence Management on Green Performance

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Abstract:- Although electronic mail management has been advantageous, the organization experiences circulation of mail and problems with less effective and effective mail management because green management has yet to be fully implemented. Sixty correspondence management employees, all research responders, from the Directorate General of Minerals and Coal comprised the research population. Questionnaires based on variable indicators were distributed to collect data, which was then processed using the Structural Equation Model-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) method. The study's conclusions show that green management has a favourable and substantial impact on green performance and green competence. Green Management has a positive and significant impact on Green Performance through Green Competency. Mail management has a positive and significant impact on Green Performance and Green Competence. Green competency has a substantial and positive impact on green performance.

Keywords:- *Electronic Mail Management, Green Competency, Green Management, Green Performance.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Green management is an approach to business management that keeps the environment in mind. Academics are becoming concerned with the idea of "green management." Green management demonstrates the development of green business, which, when implemented in an organisation, can both be profitable for the business and prevent negative effects on the community and social environment. Green management is essential to maintaining the planet Earth's environmental quality [1].

Companies frequently look for candidates who possess a particular set of skills that align with what is needed to carry out a given job. For instance, jobs requiring accounting expertise require financial knowledge. Beyond these technical skills particular to a given job, however, there are some skills that employers almost always look for [2]. In light of this assertion, it is imperative to possess an adequate number and quality of human resources. It is evident from the current situation that there is still a need for intermediate experts—that is, staff members with specialised training in archiving. There were only 2 (3%), or special archiving personnel, under the current conditions. This intermediate expert should ideally make up at least 10% of the entire staff in this correspondence management section, according to the Head of the General Division. Several researchers [3], [4], [5] have emphasised the

significance of green management, which gives employees a functional role in their work and a significant obligation to protect the environment. Despite this viewpoint, research has been done and found that GHRM (Green Human Resources Management) techniques are crucial to attaining green performance. Green management is necessary because it plays a significant role in producing the environmental quality of Earth, and it can be applied to all facets of life [6].

Environmental awareness has an impact on environmental regulatory formulations, as previous research demonstrates. Green management, green marketing, and green business are necessary and grow in importance as business competencies to produce environmental quality on Earth. These competencies can be applied to all aspects of life with a vision of sustainability if the business is to survive. Additional research examines the state of green HR practices, including environmental training, green hiring, performance reviews, employee engagement, and compensation, to promote pro-environmental behaviour in businesses. It is shown that interdepartmental learning and top management support are crucial for fostering green behaviour among staff members [7] [8].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Environmental awareness has an impact on environmental regulatory formulations, as previous research demonstrates. Green management, green marketing, and green business are necessary and grow in importance as business competencies to produce environmental quality on Earth. These competencies can be applied to all aspects of life with a vision of sustainability if the business is to survive. Additional research examines the state of green HR practices, including environmental training, green hiring, performance reviews, employee engagement, and compensation, to promote pro-environmental behaviour in businesses. It is shown that interdepartmental learning and top management support are crucial for fostering green behaviour among staff members [7]. Organizations frequently publish comprehensive reports on their environmental performance as they strive to become "greener" [9].

Green management is necessary because it is an important part of the ability to produce environmental quality of planet earth. Green management can be divided into several dimensions, namely (1) Green management awareness (2) Green management ability and (3) Green management behavior. Furthermore, the three dimensions are detailed as follows: Green management awareness [10]: Green

management awareness means that the organization accepts green values, environmental protection and environmental friendliness at a conscious level. As indicators of green management awareness are: (1) Green management concept: How organizations regard environmental protection as their own duty and how organizations take the concept of green management as one of the business objectives of the organization (2) Green management system: How the organization has formulated a detailed green management system and strictly implemented it (3) Green education and training: How the organization arranges green education and training courses to cultivate employees' green ideas and behaviors (4) Green management ability: which mainly measures the influence of management awareness and management ability on the environment. (4) Green management behavior: The green management behavior that determines the implementation of the organization is mainly divided into two main factors: internal governance and external environment.

Electronic Government (e-government) is an effort to utilize information and communication technology to improve efficiency and effectiveness, transparency and government accountability in providing better public services [11]. E-government as a form of public service organized through a government website where the domain used also shows the domain of the Indonesian government, namely go.id. In addition, e-government is the use of information and communication technology to promote a more efficient and cost-effective government, then facilitate services to the general public and make the government more accountable to the community. E-government as the use of technology based on WEB (network), internet communication, and in certain cases is an interconnection application to facilitate communication and expand access to and or from the provision of government services and information to the population, the business world, job seekers, and other governments, both institutional and interstate [12]. E-governance is a form of support for the running of e-government by emphasizing the relationship between government, society and the private sector based on information technology. In addition, egovernance also emerges as a form of e-government so that the condition of e-governance is strongly influenced by the condition of e-government [13]. The e-government policy in Indonesia is regulated more clearly in Presidential Regulation No. 95/2018 on Electronic-Based Government Systems (SPBE). This Perpres was made to realize quality public services and clean, effective, transparent and accountable governance based on electronics. The information and communication technology (ICT) revolution provides an opportunity for the government to innovate the development of the state apparatus through the implementation of an Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) or e-Government, which is the administration of government that utilizes ICT to provide services to government agencies, state civil apparatus, business people, communities and other [14].

The concept of digital governance or e-governance consists of two important elements, namely governance as the main concept and electronic or ICTs (Information and

Communication Technologies) as a tool to improve the governance process. In addition to encouraging the optimization of services to all relevant stakeholders, this is also done to increase employee productivity and create orderly administration within the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources. For an organization in both the public and private sectors, the distribution of incoming and outgoing mail in a process of business and administrative activities is an ongoing activity that also supports the sustainability of the organization. Mail management, which starts from receiving letters followed by mobilizing, numbering, recording and distributing or sending letters, needs to be organized to be efficient and effective. The activity of correspondence is usually carried out to be able to facilitate communication that is written. The form of written communication that usually occurs is in the form of official documents which are dominated by incoming letters and outgoing letters. In the past, a letter was identical to a writing on paper that contained information, either messages or news to be conveyed to other agencies or people. In practice, correspondence activities used to be very time and energy consuming because in the process everything was still done manually. Before the Electronic Service Manuscript (Naskah stands for "Naskah Dinas Elektronik") application at the Directorate General of Mineral and Coal of the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources in managing official documents using the official correspondence and archives application. This application in its use only registers incoming letters, provides numbering of outgoing letters and stores the contents of letter information without storing its digital form. So that incoming and outgoing documents or letters the original document is not stored in the application, but the document or letter is sent to the recipient's destination by sending the original physical form. However, if the operator will save the document or letter, it must be transferred from conventional to digital files [13].

The relationship between Green Management and Green Performance has been investigated in several past studies [15], [16], [17]. Based on several theories and from previous research, where green employee performance is influenced by Green Management, the researchers propose the hypothesis used in this study as follows

➤ *H1: Green Management has a Positive Effect on Green Performance*

The effect of Green Management on Green Competence has been investigated in several previous studies and led to the conclusion that Green Management has a positive effect on Green Competence [18], [19], [20]. Based on several previous studies, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

➤ *H2: Green Management has a Positive Effect on Green Competence*

The relationship between correspondence management and competence has been investigated in several previous studies with different research backgrounds. Previous studies have concluded that correspondence management has a positive effect on competence [21], [22], [23], [24], [25]. Based on these studies, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

➤ *H3: Correspondence Management has a Positive Effect on Green Competence*

The effect of correspondence management on performance has been investigated in several previous studies and led to the conclusion that correspondence management has a positive effect on performance [26], [27], [28]. Thus, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

➤ *H4 : Correspondence Management has a Positive Effect on Green Performance*

The relationship between Green Competency and Green Performance has been examined in several previous studies with various backgrounds and different times. Some previous researchers have concluded that Green Competencies have a positive effect on Green Performance [19], [20], [27], [29], [30], [31], [32]. Thus, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

➤ *H5 : Green Competency has a Positive Effect on Green Performance*

Competence as an intervening variable has been studied in several previous studies, such as research in the transmigration ministry [33], research on Islamic banks [34], research conducted on transportation department employees [35] and research conducted in manufacturing companies [36]. Based on the results of previous research, the authors propose a hypothesis related to Competence as an intervening variable as follows:

➤ *H6: Green Management has a Positive Effect on Green Performance through Green Competence*

➤ *H7:Correspondence Management has a Positive Effect on Green Performance through Green Competence.*

Based on the literature review and theories from several articles in published journals, the authors describe the framework of this research as follows:

Fig 1 Research Framework

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The approach used in this research is quantitative with survey method. This activity was carried out by analyzing directly at the Office of the Directorate General of Mineral and Coal of the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources. . This study is intended to obtain data, especially matters relating to Electronic Mail Management, and Green Management-Based Competencies, and their Effect on Employee Green Performance. The research was conducted from March 2023 to September 2023. The population in this study were all correspondence management employees within the Directorate General of Mineral and Coal. Based on data obtained by researchers, employees in this field totaled 60 employees. The questionnaire was distributed to all 60 employees from the total population. Taking all members of

the population is a census method (saturated sample), namely taking the entire population without regard to the strata in that population. This method was carried out in this study, because population members were considered homogeneous [37].

The data collected to support this research is data that is actually obtained from sources that are trusted in its validity, they are: primary data and secondary data. The data analysis used in this research is descriptive, which is obtained directly from the Office of the Directorate General of Mineral and Coal with the object of the problem under study, namely and then communicated with theories that are in accordance with the research problem of Electronic Messaging Management, and Green Management-based Competencies, and their Effect on Employee Green Performance. The analysis was continued using the help of SEM-PLS software version 4.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After obtaining data from respondents, characteristics were obtained according to the tabulation of questionnaires that had been distributed, namely, gender, latest education, position, and length of service.

Table 1 Description of Respondents

	Item	Total	%
Gender	Male	37	62%
	Wanita	23	38%
Education	High School	34	57%
	Diploma 3	2	3%
	Bachelor of Social	22	37%
	Bachelor of Computer	1	2%
	Bachelor of Social	1	2%
Title	Administrative Staff	49	82%
	Personnel Staff	3	5%
	Admin Coordinator	1	2%
	Finance	1	2%
	Archivist	1	2%
	Legal	1	2%
	Inspector	1	2%
	Administration	2	3%
	Policy	1	2%
	Age	< 30	4
30-34		9	15%
35-39		6	10%
40-44		3	5%
45-49		3	5%
50-54		15	25%
55-59		20	33%
Period of Employment	<5	3	5%
	5 - 9	9	15%
	10 - 14	15	25%
	15 - 19	7	12%
	20 - 24	2	3%
	25 - 29	9	15%
	30 - 34	11	18%
	35 - 39	4	7%

Source: Research Data (2023)

Based on the results of the data processed by the researcher, the respondents who participated in the study were mostly male respondents. This is shown in the table above which illustrates that male respondents dominate 62% of the total respondents. In addition, respondents who participated in this study generally had an education up to high school. In accordance with the data obtained from the organization, about 57% of the employees at the research locus have education up to high school.

The position of the respondents involved in this study is dominated by respondents who have the position of Administration Staff. Based on the data in the table above, the number of respondents with the position of Administration

Staff is 82% of all respondents who participated in this study. Meanwhile, the largest age group of respondents is the age range 55-59 years, which is 33% followed by the age range 50-54 years, which is 25%. In total, these two age groups accounted for almost half of the respondents at 48%. Employees with tenure between 10-14 years accounted for the largest number of respondents at 25%. The combined 5-9 age group, 10-14 age group and 15-19 age group accounted for more than half of the respondents at 52%. This means that most of the respondents have been working in their respective workplaces for quite some time and already understand the work and the organization that houses them. Calculations using the SEM-PLS method in this study resulted in qualified outer loading as shown in the following table.

Table 2 Outer Loading Results

Item	Outer Loading	Item	Outer Loading
X111	0.726	Y111	0.800
X112	0.738	Y112	0.810
X113	0.706	Y121	0.894
X121	0.788	Y122	0.822
X122	0.700	Y131	0.847
X131	0.766	Y132	0.806
X132	0.747	Y211	0.782
X133	0.747	Y212	0.783
X134	0.793	Y213	0.781
X211	0.840	Y221	0.707
X212	0.896	Y222	0.828
X213	0.895	Y223	0.728
X221	0.721	Y231	0.756
X222	0.881	Y232	0.819
X223	0.786	Y233	0.785
X231	0.852	Y234	0.813
X232	0.872	Y235	0.787
X234	0.864		

Source: Research Data (2023)

From the table above, it can be seen that all outer loadings generated by SEM-PLS calculations meet the rule of thumb requirements, which are above 0.7, so it can be said that all question items used in this study can be declared valid.

Fig 2 Path Diagram

From the figure above, it can be seen that there is a close relationship between the latent variable and each of its indicators, which then these calculated numbers will be tested with the inner model test (convergent validity and discriminant validity test) before proceeding to the inner model test.

The discriminant validity test performed is using HTMT (Heterotrait-monotrait), as shown in the following table. HTMT is defined as the average value of item correlations between constructs relative to the (geometric) average correlation for items measuring the same construct. Discriminant validity issues arise when the HTMT value is high, at 0.85 [38].

Table 3 Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

Variable	X1	X2	Y1	Y2
X1				
X2	0.159			
Y1	0.320	0.415		
Y2	0.413	0.621	0.839	

Source: Research Data (2023)

From the table above, it can be seen that the existing values are all below 0.85, so it can be said that the discriminant validity requirements have been met. Variance inflation factor The variance inflation factor (VIF) is often used to evaluate the collinearity of formative indicators. A VIF value of 5 or more indicates a critical collinearity problem among the formatively measured construction indicators Collinearity issues [38].

Table 4 Collinearity Statistics (VIF)

Variable	Y1	Y2
X1	1.007	1.150
X2	1.007	1.208
Y1		1.372

Source: Research Data (2023)

The VIF value should below 5 (five) [38], and the results of the VIF value in this study of all items show a number below 5 (five) which is the ideal Thus it can be stated that there is no collinearity issue in the data of this research. The criterion used for inner model analysis in this study is the R² value, with the interpretation of R² used as follows [38]: (1) R² value of 0.75 indicates a strong model (substantial) (2) R² value of 0.50 indicates a moderate model (3) R² value of 0.25 indicates a weak model (weak).

Table 5 R-Square

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Y1	0.271	0.246
Y2	0.754	0.740

Source: Research Data (2023)

The R-square (R²) value obtained from calculations made using PLS software bootstrapping method in the table above for Y1 is in the weak category, which is below the benchmark number 0.5, while for Y2 it is in the strong category (substantial) because it is above the benchmark number 0.75. From the results of R² testing that has been carried out, it can be seen that the model formed can be said to be robust. The next analysis used Bootstrapping analysis to get the significance of the path coefficient value of each variable used in the study. The results of the calculation with PLS for the Path Coefficients are presented in the following table.

Tabel 6 Path Coefficient (Bootstrapping)

Hipotesis		(O)	DEV	O/DEV)	P
Direct Effect					
H2	Effect of X1 on Y2	0.232	0.076	3.037	0.003
H1	Effect of X1 on Y1	0.323	0.119	2.716	0.007
H3	Effect of X2 on Y1	0.383	0.105	3.638	0.000
H4	Effect of X2 on Y2	0.347	0.07	4.957	0.000
H5	Effect of Y1 on Y2	0.561	0.088	6.395	0.000
Indirect Effect					
H6	Effect of X1 on Y2 through Y1	0.413	0.095	4.343	0.000
H7	Effect of X2 on Y2 through Y1	0.562	0.077	7.277	0.000

Original Sample (O); Standard Deviation (STDEV); T Statistics (|O/STDEV|); P Values (P)

Source: Research Data (2023)

From the results shown in the path coefficient table shown above, the overall result has a positive value, which means that if there is an increase in the exogenous variable, the endogenous variable will also increase by the path coefficient value. All path coefficient values have a P value below the 0.05 limit, which indicates that all path coefficient values are significant. The alternative hypothesis (H1) in this study that Green Management (X1) affects Green Performance (Y2), is accepted with a path coefficient value of 0.232 with a P value <0.05. The findings in this study reinforce the findings of several previous researchers, namely the results of research showing that quality management has a positive effect on green process innovation [15], [39], [40], as well as the development of green product knowledge into green business-oriented businesses that produce green products [41] and environmentally friendly management can improve sustainable performance [42].

The alternative hypothesis (H2) in this study that the Management of Securities (X2) has an effect on Green Competence (Y1), is accepted with a path coefficient value of 0.323 with a P value <0.05. The findings in this study reinforce the findings of several previous researchers, namely Green Infrastructure and Green Economy have provided benefits and influence on the environmental, social, economic pillars of sustainable development (Khoshnava et al., 2020) Furthermore, correspondence management has also been proven to improve officer competence [43].

The alternative hypothesis (H3) in this study that correspondence management (X2) affects green competence (Y1), is accepted with a path coefficient value of 0.383 with a P value <0.05. The findings in this study strengthen the findings of several previous researchers, namely in the research on correspondence management on the competence of library staff (Suarna et al., 2018; Sulistyanto, Djamil, Sutawijaya, et al., 2021) and research on correspondence management at universities with official letter information systems that can improve competence [23].

The alternative hypothesis (H4) in this study that correspondence management (X2) affects green performance (Y2), is accepted with a path coefficient value of 0.347 with a P value <0.05. The findings in this study strengthen the findings of several previous researchers, namely the application of correspondence management to improve performance in administrative services in higher education [26], [44] and correspondence management on performance in health service offices [27].

The alternative hypothesis (H5) in this study that Green Competence (Y1) affects Green Performance (Y2), is accepted with a path coefficient value of 0.561 with a P value <0.05. The findings in this study reinforce the findings of several previous researchers who examined Green Competencies in employees at universities (Anwar et al., 2020) and research that has been conducted in Iran which has proven that Green Competencies affect Green Performance [30].

The alternative hypothesis (H6) in this study that Green Management (X1) affects Green Performance (Y2) through Green Competence (Y1), is accepted with a path coefficient value of 0.413 with a P value <0.05. The findings in this study reinforce the findings of several previous researchers that competence is able to act as a mediator of the effect of green management on green competence [45] and previously also proposed by research in Pakistan [46] which examines the mediating role of competence.

The alternative hypothesis (H7) in this study that Order Management (X2) affects Green Performance (Y2) through Green Competence (Y1), is accepted with a path coefficient value of 0.562 with a P value <0.05. The findings in this study reinforce the findings of several previous researchers that competence is able to act as an intervening variable (Pramono & Prahiawan, 2021) and a group of researchers from Indonesia in a previous study [36], competence has been shown to be able to act as an intervening variable of performance.

V. CONCLUSION

From the results of the research that has been conducted related to the variables involved, it can be concluded as follows: (1) Green Management has a positive and significant effect on Green Performance, meaning that an increase in the aspects of Green Management will have an impact on a significant increase in Green Performance on employees (2) Green Management has a positive and significant effect on Green Competence, meaning that an increase in the aspects of Green Management will have an impact on a significant increase in Green Competence on employees (3) Order Management has a positive and significant effect on Green Competence, meaning that an increase in the aspects of Order Management will have an impact on a significant increase in Competence on employees (4) Order Management has a positive and significant effect on Green Performance, meaning that an increase in the aspects of Order Management will lead to a significant increase in Green Performance in employees (5) Green Competence has a positive and significant effect on Green Performance, meaning that an increase in the aspects of Green Competence will lead to a significant increase in Green Performance in employees (6) Green Management has a positive and significant effect on Green Performance through Green Competence, (6) Green Management has a positive and significant effect on Green Performance through Green Competence, meaning that an increase in the aspects of Green Management will lead to a significant increase in Green Performance through Green Competence in employees (7) Order Management has a positive and significant effect on Green Performance through Green Competence, meaning that an increase in the aspects of Order Management will lead to a significant increase in Green Performance through Green Competence in employees.

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